

Parmagnetic Resonance in Gamma-irradiated Potassium Sulphate

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Free radical production in gamma irradiated alkalthiosulphates^{1,2} and tetrathionates³ has been shown by electron spin resonance. The alkali sulphates were exposed to gamma radiation with the hope of detecting the formation of free radicals containing sulphur and oxygen. Preliminary experiments with potassium sulphate indicated that longer exposure periods were necessary in order to produce appreciable resonance signals. The exposure periods were varied from 1-8 months, corresponding to absorbed doses of the order of 10^{21} ev per gram.

Analar Reagent potassium sulphate (Mallinckrodt sample) was irradiated in the "Gamma cell 220 CO⁶⁰ Irradiation Unit" manufactured by the Atomic Energy Commission of Canada Ltd. The exposure dose rate was of the order of 10^5 roentgens per hour. A Varian associates V 4500 EPR spectrometer equipped with an X-band microwave bridge was used for recording the ESR spectra at room temperature. The experimental details are described elsewhere.¹

The e.s.r. spectrum (the first derivative of the absorption curve) consisted of a narrow absorption line with a line width ($\Delta MS'$ width between points of maximum slope taken from the first derivative plot) of about 4.0 gauss. The spectrum was slightly asymmetric and the g factor for the crossover point, as measured by including polycrystalline DPPH as internal standard was 2.0036 ± 0.0007 . Electron spin concentrations were measured by graphical double integrations of the recorded spectra and comparison, at identical instrument settings through a substandard of gamma irradiated barium dichloro acetate (1.5×10^{-2} molar in spins), with solutions of DPPH in benzene. There was a slight increase in the electron spin concentration with the absorbed dose. At an absorbed dose of 4.82×10^{21} ev per gram, the spin concentration was found to be 1.42×10^{17} spins per gram and the value was 1.68×10^{17} at a dose of 18.72×10^{21} ev per gram.

The g value of 2.0036 obtained for potassium sulphate is slightly higher than the free spin value of 2.0023. Although the spectrum has been drawn at a single microwave frequency, the g value indicates that there is almost complete quenching of orbital momen-

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1. Eager and Mahadevappa, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1963, 41, 2106.
2. *Idem.*, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 222.
3. *Idem.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1965, 34, 147.

tum in the free radical. The small g shift from the free spin value could further mean that the odd electron is not involved with a sulphur atom⁴. Chantry *et al.*⁵ have reported on the optical and e.s.r. spectra of gamma irradiated single crystals of sodium dithionate, sulphamic acid, potassium sulphamate, potassium amine sulphonate and potassium methane disulphonate. The e.s.r. spectra are similar for all these compounds, consisting of a single absorption line with an isotropic g value of 2.004. They present conclusive evidence that the e.s.r. spectrum is due to the presence of SO_3^- free radical ions in the irradiated crystal. A complete investigation of the 33 , hyperfine interaction was carried out only for the most favourable case, potassium methane disulphonate $\text{K}_2(\text{CH}_2(\text{EO}_3)_2$ and the expected intensity ratio of the $33_{\text{SO}_3^-}$ to $32_{\text{SO}_3^-}$ lines was confirmed in all cases except $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ for which the 33 , lines appeared to be too weak, these authors suggest that in sodium dithionate the $32_{\text{SO}_3^-}$ spectrum may be overlapped by that of some other radical. The present work shows that the g value obtained for the e.s.r. spectrum of gamma irradiated potassium sulphate is the same, within the limits of experimental error as the value reported for dithionate. By comparing the two spectra, it can be tentatively assumed that the magnetic centre in gamma irradiated potassium sulphate is SO_3^- ion.** Irradiation of the solid produces S-O bond scission and the resulting fragments are trapped in the poly crystalline matrix. Absence of 33 , hyperfine lines in the spectrum could be attributed to the random orientation of the radical bonds present in the micro-crystalline sample employed, with respect to the applied magnetic field, resulting in a 'smearing out' of the hyperfine structure.

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4. Gardner and Franklin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 3279.

5. Chantry *et al.*, *Mol. Phys.*, 1962, **5**, 232.

In their recent e.s.r. experiments on x-irradiated single crystals of potassium sulphate, Gromov and Merton (*Canad. J. Chem.*, 1966, **44, 327) have confirmed the existence of SO_3^- radical ions in the irradiated crystal at room temperature.